

12:30 - 14:00	Session 10: Galaxy Formation across Decades of Physical Scales	Chair: Takahiro Morishita (STScI)
12:30 - 13:00	10a Invited Talk: Tommaso Treu (UCLA)	Galaxies and Dark Matter
13:00 - 13:15	10b Danilo Marchesini (Tufts)	SMF2020: The Ultimate Wedding-Cake Measurements of the Stellar Mass Functions of Galaxies since $z=6$
13:15 - 13:30	10c Eric Bell (Univ of Michigan)	Small-scale cosmology with satellite galaxies in the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope Era
13:30 - 13:45	10d Katy Rodriguez Wimberly (UCI)	Ultrafaint Dwarf Galaxies: Smallest Scales Quenching & Predictions
13:45 - 14:00	10e Yuanyuan Zhang (Fermilab)	Studying the diffuse light components of galaxies and galaxy clusters using a stacking method
14:00 - 14:15	Concluding Remarks	

Session 10 live captioning on Friday, 9 October 2020

We are going to start the final session of our galaxy formation and evolution in the era of nancy grace roman space telescope conference. For the final session we have five talks that will be chaired by Takahiro, I will turn the floor over and he will get back to me at the end and we will have some q&a.

Hi, everyone, this is **Takahiro Morishita** and I am honored to share this session, session 10, galaxy formation across physical scales. A couple of reminders, if you have questions go to the slack channel and you will find threads for each speaker and you can ask questions there. i will give you a five minute reminder for everybody's talk, for invited talk i will give you a ten minute reminder. With that said, it's my pleasure to introduce the first speaker **Tommaso Treu** from UCLA who is going to talk about galaxy models. Take it away.

Tommaso: All right, good. So, one of the amazing things of the nancy grace roman space telescope is that it will make even the rarest of astronomical objects prominent. some of these rare astronomical objects like strong gravitational lenses are like shamrocks, finding one is hard, but when you find it it gives unique information that you don't have access to in any other way. and i will discuss, i will give you a glimpse for the kind of information we will be able to get with the nancy grace roman space telescope using strong gravitational lenses and what we can learn about the relationship between galaxies and dark matter. In turn, learning about this relationship tells us about how galaxies form and also technology. here's a brief outline of my talk, first i will give a brief introduction and review of what's the interplay between dark matter and, and in particular massive galaxies which are the most common and review the current state of affairs, what we can learn from massive galaxy information, the applications for stellar mass function and applications. i will then turn to the nancy grace roman space telescope and turn to the opportunities and challenges we need to face in order to make the most of this amazing spacecraft. so let's start from theory simulations. apologies if i am butchering it but i will give you a brief summary. What happens for dark matter

only simulations is well-established, we know that dark matter halos have a very specific profile, there's little variation from case to case but overall it's almost universal. assuming a standard contact matter particle, you end up with profiles. what is interesting is when you add baryons to it, adding baryons breaks the massive variance so the only depends on the concentration mass relation which depends on the density of the universe. when you have variance, so things happen on a very interesting. for example, baryons can cool and this leads to the loss of energy, the compression the halo. that energy can also be injected from processes like supernova explosions and that leads to the position of energy leading to expansion. another mechanism is accretion of satellites, if you have a dense satellite when it creates to a bigger black matter halo it can lead to expansion. these things are going to modify the underlying dark matter halo and vice versa of course, the dark matter halo is what creates the environment for these processes to happen. so we need to consider the components together if we have any hope to understand galaxy formation. i want to show you a brief video, obviously a picture is worth a thousand words. a video is worth at least a million. this is from the collaboration, it's scribing formation of a massive elliptical galaxy. you can see the phenomena taking place, mergers between galaxies, you have accretion of satellites, you have star formation going on, you have accretion. a few things here are particularly striking to me. the first one is that any one of these pictures kind of looks like a real picture from hubble, this simulation makes an amazing, amazing, amazing progress. this is something that a few years ago but just not possible, now we can simulate big chunks of the universe. with the resolution to describe and the resolve individual galaxies. then you can see there's some star formation going on elsewhere and major mergers, and eventually you see a lot of these things coalesce in forming one big massive galaxy. and the formation of massive galaxies, how do you end up with massive galaxies like this? that are red and dead, mostly comprised of old stars. and it's related to the relationship between periodic components and dark matter. happy ending, you end up with a nice galaxy, we have to wait for the final credits. you have it here, thank you very much, but of course it's not just looking at pictures, it's also compare the outcome of the simulation to observation. one of the most important ones is a mess profile and how this can be used in star formation diagnostic. you can see the a profile of a simulated density slope, dark matters, stars, and gas. we all know gas -- what's striking to me is the fact that stars are sub dominant, we will come back to that later in the talk. on the right-hand side, there is comparison between the profile slope which is the slope of the green component with gamma prime, and other properties like stellar mass content. we find the simulation finds that well-known results, the mass density profile with the slope close to minus 2, and they seem to agree pretty well with the observations. so for example the point there in red and gray are simulations, and a blue streak, the points are data and the blue is simulation. maybe a little bit of an offset and we will come back to that often. i think this is amazing, the fact that these can be done and are quite successful. these comparisons teach us a lot about galaxy formation, so this diagram change the parameters, the most remarkable one what happens when you turn off black holes? those are the green dotted lines, when you turn off black holes you end up not suppressing enough star formation and end up with over cooling dark matter, the dark matter gets to steep because you are cooling too much gas. so this tells you you need black hole feedback. can we go even further and separate dark matter, we need more probes and the probes we use for that are probes we need to go subcu low product solutions, i will not talk about x-rays and sunlight kinematics, at the moment i will talk about -- there's been an amazing improvement in tools in the last few years. now, tools have been able to model the extended sources, you can see to the left are images of real lenses, to the right reconstructed and you can see we can separate the lens from the deflector. you can reconstruct the source. and usually this gives the consistent with noise or features that are noninteresting for exercise. what you can get from this kind of high quality tool is a measurement of the mass which can be one or 2% precision and quality similar to the slope of the total mass density profile, you get. coupling that with stellar kinematic information from weak lensing and hierarchal framework you can decompose the individual mass density profile into their dark matter and stars and components. you can see two things, one is that the gray and blue lines usually add up to a simple in red that is consistent with the profile, but the seller component seems to be a little higher, and what we saw earlier on. so this is a quantification of how close to a parallel is the mass density profile. within 5% of parallel which would be relevant. is the halo being contracted or expanded, and it turns out it's practically zero. it's very close to unperturbed nsw, all the recipes you may be familiar with from various form of compression in star formation are all ruled out. the net effect is for some reason expansion and contraction compensate each other perfectly. the star formation efficiency as director of the amount of stellar mass divided by the available variance is relatively high, close to as high as one can get but reasonable. and we can also see the gradient, it turns out there is not significant gradient in the stellar population but we can see the significance. so comparison with simulations, plotted there as bands or lines, individual points in red and they all seem to lie on one side of the simulation. they all seem to lie on the side of the 3d dark matter fraction that is lower than simulation. so it seems that the simulation kind of leaves too much dark matter in there. remember when we said we turn off black

holes, they leave too little dark matter. in this case they leave too much dark matter, that is why it's showing how the dark matter component was too dominant with respect to the stellar components. there seems to be recipes and understanding of feedback is quite not perfect yet. it's amazing that we can make these kind of comparisons but we are not quite there yet, there's something else that needs to be tweaked. and this is another way of saying this, the projected dark matter fraction is different between the observation and simulation. and this is, you can use the stellar mass ratio as a probe of the stellar imf you find they tend to have an imf that is heavier. so i want to take a little detour and say that understanding the mass distribution in elliptical galaxies not just adjusting for galaxy formation itself but also for cosmology. you might have heard that there's a big tension between as determined by the early universe probes like cosmic microwave background and big bang, and late universe probes like seti or lasers. it turns out to be true, if it turns out to be not the result of systematic, means that the paradigm needs to have some component that changes the evolution between say the combination and present day. which is not an easy thing to do, and there is not an easy explanation for how to do it. so this is something that has had people scratch their heads for a while. and this gives you a way to address it. when you look at an object and image like in this case, if the object is variable the light rays will not arrive at the same time because the light is a different length, so if you observe a source of agreeable time like a supernova or quasar, you can measure the length of the light path in absolute units, because you measure time in seconds. and therefore you can get the size of the universe. you get the red shift and from that you could expansion. when we did the analysis using the stand up and constant mass which i've shown you is a pretty good description of all the data we have so far, we find a number that is in variable from agreement with the measurement and in the last year we've taken an effort to say well, this assumption lead us to invalidate cdm we need to revisit the assumption. invalidating is something that requires a lot of confirmation in order to throw off the model. and so we show that if we give up the assumption of power law and go to a model where we don't make any assumption and throw away basically most of the lensing information, and only use kinematics, they are about increased significance and they become not in tension with cdm anymore. so what needs to be done? what needs to be done is increased sample size of time delay lenses but also use other lenses that are not time variant to learn about the structure of elliptical galaxies and by doing that we can improve the overall position. so for example if we had 200 nontimes lenses we will be able to get 2% precision without -- of course, we need to find them but also find solution imaging. so what is nancy grace roman telescope going to do for us? the current samples are too small to determine mass on red shift and too small to determine. and this is just to illustrate the point, state-of-the-art from 2015 where we showed that everything you can do at that time, the contours are too large, change with red shift. with nancy grace roman we will have HST quality images for a large chunk of the sky. and that means that we will have an estimated 20,000 galaxy galaxy strong lenses and quadrupally image quasars in high latitude surveys which is exactly what you need to do the survey we want to. it will be really revolutionary, imagine you have 20,000 galaxies instead of the 20 i showed you the results from earlier. you cannot only measure the mass density profile of luminous and dark matter once, but you can do it as a function of red shift, as a function of mass, as a function of stellar mass, all sorts of things become possible and so you can really put to the test any galaxy information. and one important thing is that when you have a lot of shamrocks, you may find the ones that are even more rare. for example we know that spirals are about one-tenth of lenses, and so at the present time we know about 20 but with nancy grace roman we will know 2,000. we will be able to do amazing things about the mass density profile, not just elliptical galaxies but also spirals. and start to dissect. so what are the challenges ahead in order to fulfill the promise of nancy grace roman? i think we have to be, you know, careful about this because we have to be in a position where we put ourselves in a position to be able to exploit this wealth of data. finding the lenses in images i think it's something we know how to do, we've done it many times, we've done it on worse quality images. so i think that's a solved problem. of course everything can be improved but that doesn't worry me very much. getting redshifts, you need to measure the red shift and fortunately, roman space telescope will have a tool that will suffice. one of the bottlenecks will be stellar kinematics, in some cases we will be able to do the space telescope, so we will need ground-based hopefully ao assisted spectroscopy. takahiro: 10 minutes. tommaso: sorry, you scared me. some help will come from ground-based as well. another challenge we have to face is modeling speed, and i'll show you a slide next about that. this is work in progress but it's something we need to work on if we want to be able to get to 20,000 lenses from which to extract information. and one other thing we have to do for if he is to measure time delays, at present time we are using 2-meter class telescopes but the number of lenses goes up and we want to reach for a deeper lenses as well we need a dedicated three or 4-meter from the ground to supplement lsst. it will not probably have the cadence, the efficient cadence to determine a large number of lenses. in case you are interested, snowmass that is going on the same week as this conference there is a letter of intent. this was made by my student, and building on previous work. this is an example of image quasars, this should be impressive. this is the largest sample ever put together of

quadruple image quasars, very rare in the sky. in the past, modeling required about one full-time equivalent year of an expert modeler, we are working to get this down to a few percent of that. we are trying to get this modeled so this is the kind of improvement in modeling speed we need if we want to get to 20,000 lenses. i think it's feasible but it takes effort and preparation. let me summarize my thoughts, very rare objects, but we integrate nancy grace roman telescope and we will find a lot of them. they provide really unique insights into the structure of galaxies and cosmology because lensing is a direct probe of gravity, lensing doesn't care what is producing gravity, and the current samples show that the halo of massive galaxies are well described by unperturbed and fw, ruling out compression or expansion. the state-of-the-art simulations leave too much dark matter in the centers of galaxies, suggesting that there is still something that is not known about the feedback mechanism. and the result that may be interesting for people to use for star formation is the stellar imf of massive elliptical galaxies is inconsistent with popular models. you have more low mass stars. roman space telescope will improve the samples by two orders of magnitudes which we believe to dramatically improve understanding galaxies and cosmology with proper follow-up. so we will need to do some work to follow up and discover images by roman space telescope but it is a really, really, really delightful prospect. and i'll finish here.

Takahiro: Thank you very much, tommaso. We have a couple questions in the slot channel and we can do one or two here. The first question is from Eric Bell who is curious about the mismatch between observed and a simulated dark matter fraction. How do you decide that mass is belonging to compared to dark matter?

Tommaso: when we do the decomposition we don't need to assume any imf, the reason we are able to do decomposition is because through the extended sources and kinematics we have traces that have radial sensitivity, we can do the decomposition because we have the light and we can set normalization that converts light into mass and allow for a stellar mass gradient and a dark matter components. if we don't need to make any assumptions about the imf to make this statement. i think this statement is robust with respect to imf independent of it. and i don't really see a way out because the surface brightness is what it is we measured with hubble, the kinematics is what it is we measured with on the ground. and i don't think it's a huge deal, i think it's amazing that we've been able to get this close. and i don't think anyone would claim it would solve the problem. i think we just need a little more work on understanding and implement in feedback.

Takahiro: thank you. I think we can do one more quick question. Do you see any differences in your left model that the profiles and do you agree with simulations?

Tommaso: So in this kind of system, we don't see any evidence, the nsw works quite well and there could be small hiding inside but they aren't required, they have to be really small because if they were bigger we would see central images. the course i am also seeing higher mass systems, massive galaxy scale we don't see them.

Takahiro: thank you very much tommaso. There are more questions on the slack channel, i encourage you to go there and interact with people.

All right, let's let's move on to the next speaker. The next speaker is **Danilo Marchesini** from Tufts University who is going to talk about smf 2020, the ultimate wedding kick measurement of the stellar mass function of galaxies.

Danilo: Good afternoon everyone, I am going to present measurement of the stellar function of galaxies red shift of 6 achieved from the latest combination of several surveys. let me tell you for a second why we want to study stellar mass functions of galaxies, first off stellar mass function is arguably the most fundamental measurement for studying and understanding galaxy formation and evolution. it's integral history of stellar mass assembly and also the stellar mass function is defensive that informs and helps the models of galaxy formation and also quenching black hole growth and other feedback processes, mergers, and environment. a complete picture of how galaxies form and evolve, inevitably has to confront with the measurement of the stellar mass function of galaxies not only as a function of time but also a function of galaxy star formation activity, morphology, and environment. over the last ten years or so, great progress has been enabled by combining very deep small area surveys with shallow but wider surveys. a key element or a couple of key elements of these surveys that first have to have deep wavelength imaging from the

you band to the infrared wavelengths and also have the ability to -- so we hear, we construct sort of our ultimate wedding kick using a number of surveys, it covers almost 29 squared degrees. 24.5, in the k band and our catalog has 50 bands. outside of the altar visa which is shown here in blue, we have complementary fields with the altar visa dr one, it's a bit shallower, but it's over the entire cosmos field. a better example of the higher mass band, using 22 bands from you to irac wavelength. we have it down to came band magnitude of 23 over almost eight square degrees. we have included catalogs over to the 329 field, so this is a 90% complete down to band of 25.1 over about a quarter square degree. and finally we have included our own multi-wavelength catalog, constructed as part of the deep space program. we have used parallel pointing's and that varies a little bit but goes as deep as 27.8 magnitudes and this is again 90% complete, and the area is rather small. so putting it all together, here i'm showing the stellar mass function of galaxies. from over nine different from the lowest 1 of 0.2 all the way to the highest that is 4-6. in the bottom right, the circles represent the stellar mass function measurement using the one over v_{max} method and the solid black curve and gray regions represent the maximum we had of stellar mass functions. adopting a double sector. the gray curve represents stellar mass function and also for comparison in orange and dark red i'm showing the stellar mass function that we derived from 2013 and so you can really appreciate how the dramatic improvement that the fact that wedding kick is resulting in extending those measurements down to the lower stellar mass. so a few things i would like to point out in this figure, over five dex in stellar mass to 1, and even over a red shift of three or four. and this is a dynamic range enabled by the contracted wedding cake. in fact, the colored areas here show the stellar mass completeness of the individual surveys, so the ultra vista and in light blue you have the wedding cake lament. so the hubble allows for probing the low mass band about 1.3 dex deeper than possible with altar visa catalog. so that way you can sample the stellar mass function down. focusing on some of the results, it isn't always as robustly shows that double sector is needed to model the stellar mass galaxies, and in fact the double sector is preferred 2.5-3. if we look at massive galaxies, we see that about 3, there is evidence for an excess of a massive galaxies compared to the exponential cutoff of parametric. to highlight evolution, the purple ones being at the lowest red shift on the maroons one red shift 4-6. and so focusing at stellar mass of around 10-11, you can appreciate how quickly the number of galaxies has grown over 1.5 billion years between red shift 6 and red shift 2.5 which is shown in yellow-orange here. under this growth is about a factor of two larger than the growth over the following 8.5 billion years from red shift 2.5 down to red shift 2. on the contrary, both a very high solar masses and at the very low mass and around ten to the eight solar masses there appears to have been much less evolution in the number densities, in particular is quite interesting to see the low mass and as a function of red shift, and it's tempting to attempt and interpretation of a possible steepening of that slope with increasing red shift. but hold that thought, i'll come back to that. another way of presenting these results is by the number as a function of red shift by integrating the stellar mass down to a certain stellar mass, and this is what is shown here in this plot, so the red, orange, salmon, and dark red symbols are the new measurement. and we have the red points, salmon is down to ten to the 11th and dark red down to ten to the 11.5. really the most massive galaxies. i want to highlight the fact here that the empty circles represent the estimates of the number density will may have to extrapolate the stellar mass is down to a regime that is not directly proved by the wedding cake. the possible incompleteness is a warning. mentioned before, the growth of the number densities above ten to the 11th is faster above 2.5 and slow down with red shift below 2.5. whereas the evolution of galaxies down to the tent of the eighth is rather flat with red shift, we see a rather slow evolution of the most massive galaxies from red shift 6 to red shift 1.3 with some evidence of growth in the first 2 billion years of cosmic history down to red shift 3. and then a growth by a factor of about 6 down to red shift 0. and finally the plot on the right shows the evolution with red shift of the stellar mass density obtained by integrating the stellar mass function down to ten to the eighth solar masses, and again here the open symbol represents values where we had to extrapolate the stellar mass function. on the last compared to previous measurements of stellar mass function and number density, this represents an impressive improvement. again thanks to the constructed wedding cake. so now as i've shown before, there appears to be in excess of very massive galaxies above 3, with respect to the schechter exponential cutoff whereas on the low end there is little evolution and some evidence of the low mass and slopes deepening with increasing red shift. however, it is important to consider a possible systematic effect which might contribute in producing these observations. and one of the most obvious of such systematic effect as the mission line contamination which can bias the stellar masses, would we expect a mission line contamination to increase become larger with decreasing stellar masses and also as we go to higher red shift. we have adopted a statistical approach to correct for a mission line contamination after accounting for that in stellar masses come we obtained the plot on the right. and so here you can see that if you focus on the low mass and, although there's still remained relatively constant with red shift, it does steepening as a function of red shift with increasing red shift. red shift above 3 is somewhat reduced specially a red shift between 3 and 4. so where do we go from here? this is my last slide. so

where do we go from here? the upcoming facilities will enable significant progress, but as we saw through the many talks over this past week this research will not be without new and exciting challenges and opportunities. i have two obviously mentioned jwst, specifically there are a couple of, to me, particularly attractive observational modes. one of the deep near infrared, deep near camera imaging using the full suite of medium band filters. and i think that if you hundred square meters would probably do it. although it won't be cheap, unfortunately. to have a complete sense of quiescent galaxies, and also star-forming galaxies down to ten to the eighth. in fact, the medium band provides vastly superior photometric red shift and constrains on the spectral energy distributions, including the detection of those with strong emission lines that might bias our stellar mass estimate. another mode is the nearest spectroscopy, this is not too different from the one on hst however it's on a much more powerful telescope and also goes out to red shift 2.2 microwave length. stellar mass function studies the euclid field will really provide massively improved statistics at the high mass end we've heard of the telescope is going to be at least 100 times more efficient with spectroscopy than hst, so if you tenths of a square degree detailed or maybe quarter square degree or going to be game changers providing amazing statistics given a very extreme massive an end enabling studies of the stellar mass function of galaxies simultaneously as a function of environment, galaxy tabs, specific star formation rates and morphology. over the next decade, the counting will go on. thank you so much.

Takahiro: thank you very much, danilo. very impressive talk. We can do one question. It's very exciting to see the most massive galaxies at red shift 6. Are these massive galaxies seen in simulations?

Danilo: That's a very good question, i think simulations, the one thing that simulations are telling us is that yes, they can produce these very massive galaxies i think. However, i believe a red shift 4-6 they are entirely forming massive galaxies. and so it would be really interesting to have a way of classifying observationally whether we have a quiescent or massive galaxies that have significantly quenched star formation activity. and we do have from the photometry from some of those galaxies that have shown there we do have some indications that they have quenched star formation activity, obviously from photometric alone it's especially at those redshifts becomes really difficult to be secure and we really need to go after them. jwst will definitely help

Takahiro: thank you very much. I encourage you to go to your slack channel and interact.

Next speaker is **Eric Bell** from the University of Michigan. Eric is going to talk about small-scale cosmology with satellite galaxies in the nancy grace roman space telescope era. take it away, eric.

Eric: Great, thank you. I'd like to tell you about work that my collaborators and i have been doing over the last year, trying to understand the satellites in nearby galaxy groups with survey data sets. so we've heard during this week that dwarf galaxies in the numbers and masses, the star formation activity in the distribution spatially and kinematically, they really are the observational bedrock of our understanding of small-scale cosmology. and ultra-faint galaxies have been particularly important in enriching this conversation we've discovered as a community tens of ultra-faint galaxies which leads to an inference hundreds around the milky way. some of these are satellites, the faintest known stars defaming the back forming galaxy is one of the brighter, at lower luminosity as they appear to be uniformly old and this could tell us something really important about how galaxy formation works on a small scale. and we've used this information to try and calibrate our models to reproduce the properties, the numbers and mass profiles of milky way's and m41 faint satellites. these models are important because they are our primary source of intuition about how faint galaxies are. now, i think we all kind of appreciate that to galaxy groups is potentially dangerous for generalizing our understanding of all dwarf galaxies, so there's a number of collaborations that have been searching for satellites in nearby galaxy groups. down to both classical limits, so this is down to just under a million solar masses. and some of these searches have allowed us to start reaching into the ultra-faint regime, finding systems that are similar in mass and not finding the star-forming satellites. so looking up a number of satellites that have been found, it's interesting to note that the luminosity function or mass function of the satellites show much larger variations than we have seen between for example the milky way and m41 mass functions. m81 down to m94 have a tremendous diversity in numbers of satellites. there is a trend, if you start controlling for the mass of the main galaxy, it does appear that if i have a bigger main galaxy i'll have more satellites. but there is a plot of scatter around this. and these mass functions, these trends have allowed us to modify, steep and somewhat behavioral occupation models to more or less

reproduce this kind of behavior. but the source of scatter, it is a real scatter as far as we can tell. and it's something that we don't yet understand. and so there are a number of different ideas or pieces of physics that should be important here, so accretion, feedback, and reorganization are most sophisticated models are telling us should be important. i also want to emphasize the importance of delivery of satellite galaxies, this is an animation by dr. patel's group and what they are doing is showing the falling in of significant numbers of satellites in the magellanic group as it falls in towards the milky way, to end up within 100-kilo parcels of the milky way. this has dramatically impacted the satellite population. this accretion is important, we might expect to find in the universe a correlation between the largest satellite ever accreted, if i accrete something much bigger like half the size of the milky way i might update many more satellites. so you might expect if we were able to plot the massive satellite ever accreted whether it merged a long time ago, that i might then see a correlation with the number of satellites. and simulations this process is happening but the correlation is washed out by a number of other processes. interestingly, in the observations there is a strong trend. so galaxies that merge with large satellites, and maybe one for example is merging with m82. these have many more satellites than the type of systems then milky way and other systems which have merged with much smaller systems. this is not in the models, i think it's really interesting to try and understand and i think this could be an interesting part of what's driving scatter in this relationship between the number of satellites and the mass galaxy. so if we want to make more progress in understanding this and other issues, how much we can generalize our wisdom from the local groups to elsewhere, we need empirical guidance. particularly in the ultra-faint regime. down here we have really only the milky way and m31. so cognizant of this, our and other groups have been trying to survey the stellar halos and satellites of nearby milky way mass galaxies. many of these groups are using subaru hyper supprime-cam and using resolve star techniques to show the kind of data sets it produces, a cutout from sloan of a few hundred kilo parsecs of the m81 group. and then misses an overlay of star counts, these are red giant branch gold stars, color-coded by metallicity from red stars being more metal rich, the blue stars more metal-poor. there have been 1 kilo parcel square, so you can see in comparison with the tradition, there are red giant stars everywhere in these groups, a large extended stellar halos and m81 itself and extended from m82. so if you're interested in learning more about that, this is a nice paper about that. what i will focus on today is some of the tiny blue smudges that are down the bottom. so these are dwarf galaxies in the m81 group, so for this we have to use really aggressive star galaxy separation using both somewhat traditional and machine learning techniques. and we search for hundreds of parsecs, over densities on small scales we don't see on large scales in just metal-poor red giants. as an example of the type of system you can recover with this, this is a system of negative 7 or negative 8 dwarf in the m81 group, that we discovered a couple years ago. there are other candidates too, i'm gonna show show you a bad one. one that looks really pretty on the edge, and so both you and i, i'm sure, imagine hey, we could really do with hst follow-up make sure we understand this. we would like to confirm it and better understand. in order to understand the completeness better, we've been inserting our artificial galaxies into the catalog, rerunning the detection and seeing what we get back out. this is a plot where we have luminosity from faint to bright, size from small to big, local group galaxies are over plotted in green, and in this one we deposit some artificial ultra-faint galaxies. the ones are just not numerous enough to be detected, and gray that ones we managed to recovered are in shades of brown. this is one of many realizations, but it suffices to show that with this type of data set technique, we should be able to develop in the next two years a secure sense of worth to about negative 7, and this opens up the discovery space, remembering the faintest known star-forming galaxy it would be really neat if we were able to discover star-forming ultra-faint galaxies in the local universe that would help understand and enrich our knowledge of what type of galaxies they are. this also is very similar to m30 ones satellite census depth. so looking forward, rubin observatory plus subaru hyper supprime-cam will more or less double the number of satellite and put the other groups on the same footing as m31. now looking forward to the roman space telescope, i think we can appreciate this is going to be an enormous increment in our understanding about this type of system. here i'm showing a simulated data set from the bullock and johnston simulation, it's put in a distance of three and a half mega parsecs and five square degrees on the sky, it was about 20 hours total according to my calculations. it would be required to get catalogued. the background looks funny, and that's because what we did was used candels uds, real unresolved sources but because the field is so much larger we had to photograph 540 times, that gives us this stripe across the data set. we can do the same exercise, throw in ultra-faint galaxies, and the bottom line is that within the region near the galaxy, you actually get confused by the stellar halo itself and it can only detect galaxies at about negative 5.5 or so. but in the outer parts where you are not confused by stellar halo stars, you are really just limited by rgb star counting statistics and one can reach absolute magnitudes of negative 4. this is a factor of 100 improved over what is typical, and will dramatically push into discovery space and may allow us to find tens or even hundreds of satellites in these galaxy groups. this is my conclusion slide, just to point out that current surveys have found an unexplained and

really interesting correlation between the number of satellites and the mass of the largest merger of the group ever experienced, and that current and upcoming results should allow us to go a factor of ten deeper in terms of our satellite census. but with the roman space telescope, we should be able to improve on that by another factor of ten. i think opening up an enormous amount of space. thank you for your attention, and i will take questions.

Takahiro: thank you very much, eric. we can do one question now. Ryan Patrick is asking there's a point in the galaxy history where they can have an effect on the number of satellites expected to have. I'm thinking the merger with milky way and whether it's groups have any effect on satellite position today.

Eric: thank you for that question. it's a really interesting one. so, richard desousa and i have been thinking about this using just dark matter only simulations, so hydrogen situations there aren't many of them that will resolve systems that are low enough mass to be able to really comment on this. we are using dark matter only simulations and what we have -- i'm gonna say right now, we are still in a process of learning about the importance of time on this. what we can see is that relatively early mergers, what happens to a lot of the satellites he would gain in those they do get timely disrupted by the main galaxy in the middle and that subsequent mergers because they vary the potential a lot, lead to enhanced destruction of pre-existing satellites. i think there's potentially time right back might really matter, but it may matter more by they managed to get destroyed before i managed to see them.

Takahiro: thank you very much for your insight.

We are moving to the next speaker, who is **Katy Rodriguez Wimberly** from UCI, who is going to talk about dwarf galaxies on smaller scales and predictions. Can you share the screen?

Katy: Thank you so much! and to all of the organizers, thank you so much for having me. i am a second to last year graduate student at UCI, i work with my super and i want to talk about further specifically about the milky way ultra-faint dwarf galaxy satellites. and so as eric mentioned, we really have only seen these ultra-faint within the past 15 years, really distinct to digital surveys such as spss. i am also really excited to see what discoveries the nancy grace roman space telescope will bring us in this ultra-faint dwarf galaxy revolution. tiny galaxies are still mysterious in many ways, and the majority of them are no longer forming stars. but what stopped the new star formation from occurring and how long that took is much a mystery. so here we have a plot of satellite quenching timescales, so how long different environmental mechanisms have taken to suppress star formation of cross arrange of seller mass of satellite galaxies or various satellite galaxies. as you see on the smaller screen, we don't know anything really. if we look at ultra-faint and a couple different ways, to call main options of star formation and suppression mechanisms pop up. so looking at the star formation histories of six above her ultra-faint, these are them by tom brown in 2014, you can see all six of these have universally ancient stellar populations. so this points to the fact that maybe these ultra-faint have star formation suppressed because of the ionization. we look at these six in a different light, it points to the possibility of environmental quenching mechanisms. on the right-hand side here we have a plot from the simulation looking at subhalo's color-coded by time, those are subhalo's that have been in their host for a very long time and looking at where our ultra-faint live, this is where those live. they may have been accreted a long time ago, allowing the milky way time to environmentally quench their star formation. so this is the question that i wanted to answer: are ultra-faint been satellites long enough for the environment to have affected their star formation? i turned to elvis, something that i did with elvis is a dark matter only simulation, we know that baryons can have the distress especially some of the smallest subhalo's in a simulation and so to speed up this, i randomly destroyed some of my tiny subhalo so i cut down my parent population by about 25%. with this, statistically more realistic sample i played again. i randomly selected six subhalo's that i think would house ultra-faint dwarf galaxies and i asked if all six had fallen in by a given red shift across the red shift range and i did this 10,000 times. so this gives me a probability of environmental quenching, were these subhalo's within the host long enough for environmental effects to have quenched the star formation in their galaxies. and as you can see, as we go further back in time the probability of environmental quenching just drops dramatically. but i also considered processing, so eric showed a wonderful animation, you have tiny subhalo's and tiny satellites being part of a larger system before falling into the milky way. and so what if those magellanic clouds were able to quench, and the dashed line shows me incorporating this idea of processing into my little game, and you can see that there is a little more probability here but still not a ton. the other

thing we know is that there is definitely more than six ultra-faint month so if i increase my population to 10 or even 20, you see that the environmental quenching probability continues to plummet. so this allows me to put a pretty robust bow tie on my question, so there's a very low probability, less than .1%, that all six of our ultra-faint were environmentally quenched at red shift 1. so then i can wrap up this big picture of satellite quenching timescales by saying it is highly unlikely that the altar feigns our ultra-faint because they were quenched because of the environment, which then points to that other main mechanism which would have been during or because of the ionization, the ultra-faint had their star formation suppressed. with this, the big one in my side is that this work really heavily relies on involve times, and are the involved times we are seeing simulations what is happening irl? some current work by a former research mate of mine, who is now postdoc at university of washington, he looked at the time of our satellites on a case-by-case basis, so combining 2018 work, looking at proper motions of our satellites from the second, he put together this picture which is following what we believe. in the upper left corner of our ultra-faint, they quenched before they became satellites. and in the lower right you have the more classical, more massive satellite galaxies which were quenched because of the milky way environment. on a case-by-case basis, we are following what we think but then as we look at our lead distribution from proper motions and in a more statistical point of view, they are not matching up at all. so the black line here is cumulative distribution of infall time, and the three dashed lines are halos in three different hosts, i just wanted to highlight how a lot of this work balances on whether we are properly attributing simulations we see in the simulations to what we are seeing observationally. and again, i'm really excited to see how the roman space telescope can help us improve things, especially the rescission of our proper motion and synergy between roman and gaia. to talk about more the work i'm currently doing, i am using phat elvis, this title disruption in it. using physics, not just probability. so 12 of the phat elvis hosts heaven and vetted gravitational potential. if what i'm doing is distance matching some, so from 36 satellites i placed 10-kilo parsec been around each of the satellite distance and i randomly select ten sets of halos for each of those galaxies, from each of my three host ranges. so i break my 12 disk host from phat elvis into three bins, i have four low and subhalo's and four intermediate and four high mass that are about ten to the 12th. we can further constrain the mass of the milky ways dark matter halo through this kind of lens of -- i used the same set of distance mass subhalo's, 10 per every 36 or for each of the 36 satellites, and i look at radial velocity. these had some pretty well constrained radial velocity measurements. as you can see here, the p values are two sets from statistical tests used to compare the distribution. the p value is less than .025, you can reject the null hypothesis and as you can see, the preferred host mass set when you look at radial velocity is intermediate mass. but gaia gave us 60, so we did incorporate tangential and total velocity, this shows the preference is skewed, the p values are abysmal and the error bars are very, very high on some of these galaxies. so why did to constrain this a little bit as i cut out satellites that have very large tangential velocity errors, so now i have a more tightly constrained set of 22 satellites and i am matching and comparing their space-based. as you can see here, there is a nice reference for a more intermediate mass milky way halo than is currently canonically accepted. and just to reiterate again, i'm really excited. this large field of view that roman will have, we can get proper motions and put it in a reference frame again which will be fantastic for future. so i will leave up my summary slide, and thank you all so much.

Takahiro: all right, perfect. we can do one question. from Eric Bell, if you choose systems with only two main infall events, does that increase the chance of branching?

Katy: that's a good question. i think it can, so i didn't look into -- i looked into this idea of backplash galaxies and multiple infall's some, i didn't look specifically at how long, i think that's an interesting question to look at to see how long a subhalo is spending in the host halo before he leaves, so is their time between that early infall and the last infall for the environment to have quenched it? that range is not too large from what i remember looking into. so i don't think there is a ton of chance that an earlier infall could have had enough time to environmentally quenched. but i think that's definitely something that i would be interested to look at further.

takahiro: i encourage you to go to the select channel so you can interact with people.

Let's move on to the final speaker in this session, **Yuanyuan Zhang**. Yuanyuan is going to talk about studying the different light components of galaxies and galaxy clusters using a stacking method. Take it away.

Yuanyuan: Thank you, and thank you for the organizers for this really nice conference. With this talk, I am shifting the topic from the smallest galaxies to the largest galaxies. and in particular, I'll be focusing on the low surface brightness of diffuse light inside a galaxy cluster. This kind of light is more commonly known as intracluster light, and in the background image you can see it between the two very bright galaxies at the center of a galaxy cluster. observational studies have shown that this kind of diffuse light component exists to be much further than what you can see on this image. it'd also exist around a variety of galaxies. There have already been a few presenters that explained very nicely of why we need to study low surface brightness light and intracluster light. so just to add more material on that, here i am showing the modeling results which incorporated the diffused light in the modeling of a galaxy of stellar mass functioning and star formation rate. So on the left side of the slide, it shows the stellar mass of the dark matter halo central galaxies and its red shift evolution. on the right side it shows the diffused light component of those galaxies. so in this work, he found dark matter halo cluster size which is shown as the green line, the diffused light could be four or five times more massive than the central galaxy itself. if you go to a small mass dark matter halo, the relation seems to have reversed which is also interesting itself. so moving to the observational side of diffuse light status, like many of the previous speakers mentioned this is really not easy, and there is an lot of observational effects to consider. So on this slide, I'm showing an image of a galaxy cluster which has been searching specially for low surface brightness. on the right side of the slide, i'm showing the image after maxing out all of the known objects, right stars, all of the cluster galaxies excluding the cluster in this image. Hopefully we can use this image for measuring diffusing intracluster light but really, intracluster light what you are saying is it's left over from the bright stars and bright galaxies and if you look really hard, you can probably also see the background. so in this talk, i want to advocate measure is called a stacking, which means that take if you clusters and take an average or median of their images. This kind of method requires widefield imaging survey data, so widefield images and survey images are particularly powerful in this method. studying intracluster light, we max out all of the objects we can find in these images and stack the images together. take the average or median of these images together, so there is some disadvantages of using a stacking method. it does wash out the cluster variations, unless you really know what you are looking for the discovery space does shrink a bit. but the good thing is that all of the contamination tends to become relatively smooth that you could just subtract without removing them one by one. this method is not immune to all of the observational effects, so here i'm showing in our method we use -- we stack a bunch of random points, random locations in the survey footprint to account for the background from all of the contamination and left over. so this shows the background level as the redline, and our intracluster light measurement as the gray line. so we did find that, for example, this background could be really dependent because of cluster selection. so if we want to go to really low surface brightness level, like 30 magnitude we still need to pay attention to the methods we use of processing images. so moving on to the results, here is showing the surface brightness measurements of the intracluster light and also the bct together. as a result, you see a bright core at the center of the cluster which is related to the bct. then outside of about 20-30 milliparsecs we see transition into the envelope, that extends to about 100-kilo parsecs and after that we still see a very extended component, the diffused light component. this means that the intracluster light can really go very far. to about one mega parsecs from the cluster center. so compared to the galaxies inside galaxy clusters, intracluster light itself turns out to be quite significant component, stellar component. so here i'm showing the integrated luminosity of the cluster and intracluster light as the redline. all of the nonessential cluster light are integrated luminosity shown as the blue line. so within the central 200-kilo parsecs of the clusters, the most important component is the bcg and intracluster light. outside of the kilo parsecs, intracluster light is a significant component compared to all of the intralight galaxies. bcg and intracluster make up 30-60% of the total cluster. you can really stack anything you want to stop, so moving on to stack a bunch of luminous galaxies, the full-time by a graduate student at the university of chicago. the right side shows the lrg compared to the gcb. it does go to about 100-kilo parsecs but this extended light makes up only about 10% of the total light. which is roughly agreed with the modeling results, we probably still need to do a quantitative comparison to see how well that agrees. so, with those measurements we can start looking at other properties of intracluster light. we look at how intracluster light varies with cluster methods, so this result shows intracluster light measurements indicators. interestingly, regardless of the cluster methods, the bcg's have the same core within about 10-kilo parsecs. outside of the 10-kilo parsecs the differences start to show up. they have more diffused, more light and a difference increasing with cluster radiance and stabilizes around about 100-kilo parsecs. so it roughly agrees with what a lot of people have found that the outskirts of the clusters really strongly correlate with cluster mass. but in the end, we did find that there is a trick to make the intracluster light profiles appear the same, scaled back the cluster radius. so, this kind of profile is especially this cluster mass profile agree quite well outside of about 50-kilo parsecs, it really indicates that there is something going on with intracluster light, it's more effective than the central galaxy formation. and i think that roughly

agrees with what a lot of people have found about the correlation between diffuse light and the halo method. so there is also quite a bit of evidence that shows that there could be some radio correlation between diffuse light and clusters total mass. so we looked at this as well, all of the clusters we studied we have their lensing profiles shown as the blue lines here and we look at the intracluster light profiles. so i think that stays another indicator that we also agree on the radio profile. here is the lensing profile compared to the satellite galaxy flight profile and you can see. simulations don't seem to agree with that conclusion, intracluster light is rather steeply distributed in the simulation. i think we do need a bit more signal to tell what is really going on there. so hopefully we could resolve that. so, the next decade could be a really good time for studying the surface brightness diffuse light because lsst and euclid are going to collect 100 times more photons than what we had before. we could really map out all of the mechanisms. i'm particularly excited about infrared imaging capabilities. and finally, here's my summary slide. if anyone is interested in comparing data sets, please just let me know and i'm really happy to send whatever i can send to you so we can compare data. thank you.

Takahiro: thank you very much yuanyuan, very nice talk. so i have one quick question, in the era of roman space telescope can we constrain the stellar population of these icl or are they too faint to give such a constraint?

Yuanyuan: i think so, so one thing is that we could look at the colors of the icl, and i think there is quite a bit of evidence that the stellar population is different from the bcg's itself. that's one thing. regarding the -- there's another possibility to study icl through spectroscopic instruments. i don't know if roman is going to have it, if so, that would be great too.

Takahiro: Thank you very much for your insight. I think we need to move on, but i think more questions will be coming in the slack channel so I encourage you to go back there and interact with people. That's the last speaker, a very nice session, and i'm happy to hand over to the organizers. Thank you very much.

Russell Ryan: This is Russell, thank you very much and thank you to all the speakers and chairs of the sessions. We are going to have a couple of slides in conclusion just to wrap everything up, and Susanna will start that now.

Susana Deustua: Okay, so Russell and I have some concluding remarks we would like to share. We have learned a lot or a little bit about nancy grace roman during these five days, we learned a little bit more about the space telescope named after nancy grace and we learned a lot about where we are with galaxy formation and evolution during this conference and it's been very exciting. but let's do some numbers.

So we wanted to let you know that we had approximately 129 abstracts submitted, 102 for talks, and 27 for posters. we had 305 registered participants, which is pretty huge. and we just wanted to note that our average number of participants on the blue jeans event was on the order of 170, many people were on slack, almost all in fact. 250 per day. and on our facebook live feed we had approximately, to date, 400 persons reached per session. i just wanted to remind you that the slack and facebook statistics are all preliminary.

But we did want to let you know how the contributed talks were selected. So of those submitted, the SOC only saw the title and abstract so there was no identifying information as far as we could do so. and the SOC then selected the 36 talks. four contributed talks over nine sessions, those who were not selected were encouraged to present posters or prerecorded talks. as far as we could tell, since we didn't actually have the detailed demographic information is that the contributed talks were representative of the initial pool. of all the possible 93 possible posters, we ended up with 62 posters which is pretty phenomenal. and there was a lot of discussion on the slack channel. and then just to show you sort of the distribution by gender, the contributed talks, invited talks, and posters. females are in purple and males are yellow orange, we are just on the order between 42-45% female and male look a little bit different, which is interesting. By career stage i think the contributed talks are roughly equally divided between graduate students, early career and midcareer, and somewhat fewer on the senior career level. For the invited talks, not surprisingly we had more senior level people but there was still a pretty good representation of early and mid-career.

To remind you, after the conference the slack work space will be available for several months. All the presentations that were recorded will be available via the STScI website and also the Facebook stream will remain up for awhile. For those of you who wish to revise or update your presentations and posters, please do so and upload the revisions to box by the 23rd of october. so basically two weeks. and we are just reminding you that all the presentations, posters, the videos, and captioning will be formally archived, and we will be sending out the actual url for where you can see those things once you've got everything uploaded. and now to russell.

Russell: I just wanted to offer a number of acknowledgments, thank you to everyone who has been instrumental in making this happen. I first want to acknowledge the science organizing committee, the panel and the science discussions that includes from peter behrooze, caitlin casey, steve finkelstein. thanks again to all of the session chairs who we heard about, getting them organized. arianna cortesi, harry ferguson, jenny greene, takahiro morishita, lorenzo zanisi, Vivian U, camilla pacifica. Then I must recognize the local organizing committee who has been instrumental in all of the sort of behind the scenes things that hopefully were transparent to most of you, Susanna, Carol Christian, Thomas Marufu who really went above with the i.t. support. Max Mutchler, myself, Flory Hill, Darlene Spencer, and then we also should recognize Sherita Hanna... we lost your audio. Do you want to finish up?

Susana: I will continue, we also want to recognize the Roman Mission Office and Roman Telescope Branch at the Institute, in particular Roeland van der Marel who gave a talk on the first day, Caroline Gilbert as well as Gisella de Rosa and Jonathan Hargis, and we want to especially thank all of our captioners at CaptionMax. And most importantly, thanks to all of you for attending and participating and joining us in this five-day conference on galaxy formation and evolution, and we hope to see you all at another conference. Thanks so much, thanks everyone.

Live captioning was provided by CaptionMax. Some formatting and light editing was included by the Local Organizing Committee for added clarity, but there was no attempt to correct all live captioning errors.

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